

THE ROLE OF BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN PREDICTING THE COURSE OF DISEASE IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PREECLAMPSIA

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Abstract

This study evaluated the role of biochemical parameters in predicting the course of preeclampsia in pregnant women. A total of 130 pregnant women participated, including patients with moderate and severe preeclampsia and a healthy control group. Significant changes in hemostatic, renal, and endothelial dysfunction biomarkers were identified. Increased levels of D-dimer, fibrinogen, NGAL, and cystatin C, along with decreased ADAMTS-13, were associated with disease severity. Comprehensive assessment of these biomarkers is important for early diagnosis, evaluation of severity, and prediction of thrombotic complications in preeclampsia.

Keywords

preeclampsia, biochemical markers, D-dimer, fibrinogen, NGAL, cystatin C, ADAMTS-13, pregnancy.

Relevance

Preeclampsia is one of the most urgent problems of modern obstetrics and perinatal medicine and represents a pathological condition that poses a serious threat to maternal and fetal health. In recent years, scientific research devoted to the etiopathogenesis, diagnosis, and prognosis of this disease has expanded significantly. In particular, studying the significance of biochemical markers is considered one of the important directions for the early detection of preeclampsia and prevention of complications. Among biochemical markers, angiogenic and antiangiogenic factors are of particular

importance. Specifically, changes in the levels of sFlt-1 (soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase-1) and PlGF (placental growth factor) are important indicators of the development of preeclampsia. Increased sFlt-1 levels and decreased PlGF levels indicate impaired angiogenesis and reflect placental dysfunction.

Purpose of the study

To determine the pathogenetic significance of biochemical markers associated with the hemostatic system, endothelial dysfunction, and renal function (D-dimer, APTT, INR, PTI, fibrinogen, NGAL, cystatin C, ADAMTS-13) in pregnancy complicated by preeclampsia; to comprehensively evaluate their diagnostic and prognostic value; and to improve early diagnosis and individualized clinical management.

Materials and methods

A total of 130 pregnant women participated in this study. Among them, 50 women had moderate preeclampsia, 50 had severe preeclampsia, and 30 healthy pregnant women formed the control group. Such grouping made it possible to comparatively analyze the results, identify changes in the hemostatic system indicators at different severity levels of preeclampsia, and evaluate their clinical significance.

Discussion

The study included 100 women with preeclampsia (50 moderate and 50 severe cases) and 30 women with physiological pregnancy. The levels of D-dimer, APTT, INR, PTI, fibrinogen, NGAL, cystatin C, and ADAMTS-13 were determined. Results. Compared with the control group, significant changes in biomarkers of hemostasis, renal function, and endothelial dysfunction were observed in pregnant women with preeclampsia. The D-dimer level was 311.23 ± 26.34 ng/ml in the control group, increased to 2009.82 ± 26.92 ng/ml in moderate preeclampsia, and reached 1929.56 ± 52.54 ng/ml in severe preeclampsia. APTT shortened from 31.99 ± 0.56 s in the control group to 18.42 ± 0.48 s in moderate preeclampsia and 22.14 ± 0.42 s in severe

preeclampsia. Fibrinogen increased sharply from 338.67 ± 21.04 mg/dl in the control group to 6115.92 ± 151.66 mg/dl in moderate preeclampsia and 4214.56 ± 289.65 mg/dl in severe preeclampsia. NGAL and cystatin C levels also increased significantly, reaching 44.10 ± 1.61 U/ml and 1.90 ± 0.06 mg/l, respectively. ADAMTS-13 sharply decreased from 0.88 ± 0.10 IU/ml in the control group to 0.21 ± 0.01 IU/ml in moderate preeclampsia. Correlation analysis revealed strong associations among all markers ($r=0.65-0.81$; $p<0.01-0.001$).

Conclusion

Comprehensive assessment of biochemical markers (D-dimer, fibrinogen, NGAL, cystatin C, ADAMTS-13) has high significance in the early diagnosis of preeclampsia, determination of disease severity, and prediction of thrombotic complications.

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